

Pros and Cons of Different User Interfaces for Statistical Software

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Abstract

Statistical software programs feature very different approaches to user interfaces, ranging from entirely command line or code based to those with extensive graphical user interfaces offering point and click access to executed code, to interfaces that seek to automate analyses based on very simple user selections, or even via prompted inputs to chat bots based on large language models. This roundtable discussion covered pros and cons of various interface approaches from the perspectives of users of varying levels of statistical and programming expertise, with special attention to potential pitfalls of highly automated approaches. This summary incorporates additional input from participants in the session.

Key Words: statistical software, user interface

1. Introduction

Everyone working in any area of statistics, aside perhaps from the most abstractly theoretical, will have occasion to make use of statistical software. Many statisticians and data scientists make use of it daily. Teachers, students, and researchers in a wide variety of fields may also use it frequently. The population of users varies widely in knowledge and experience both of statistical methods and computer programming. This presents a complicated and challenging environment for developers of statistical software to navigate in creating and maintaining useful software. Here we outline a set of considerations that are relevant for creation and maintenance of high-quality statistical software and discuss the implications for a variety of types of user interfaces.

2. What makes for good statistical software?

2.1 Requirements and considerations

A number of aspects are fundamental to evaluating statistical software. The following list is partially ordered, with the first two items the most important, and others organized primarily by the order encountered in the process of analyzing data.

1. Accuracy
2. Repeatability/reproducibility of computations and analyses
3. Data input and ingestion capabilities
4. Data inspection and manipulation/transformation capabilities
5. Graphical capabilities
6. Breadth and depth of available analyses
7. Presentation of results, including creation of useful output
8. Ease of use, including accessibility
9. Documentation, including algorithmic details

2.1.1 Accuracy

Accuracy is the most important requirement for statistical software. While no software is likely to be perfect, and incorrect results will occasionally occur with any program or package, striving for accuracy is clearly the most important goal to pursue. It is also one of the most complicated things involved in programming statistical analyses. While the complexity of obtaining accurate results in highly complicated iterative analyses is probably the first thing that comes to mind when worrying about software accuracy, the nature of fixed precision floating-point computation puts bounds on how accurate even seemingly simple calculations may be. Explaining these limitations to users can be a formidable challenge as well. Avoiding unnecessary rounding and truncation of values and allowing user control over rounding where possible are useful goals.

2.1.2 Repeatability/reproducibility of computations and analyses

Along with accuracy, the ability to confirm accuracy or diagnose errors by repeating or reproducing computations and analyses is crucial to good statistical software. While always important for any scientific work, this has become even more crucial with the advent of requirements by many journals that computations be clearly reproducible and information necessary for reproduction to be made available by authors.

2.1.3 Data input/ingestion capabilities

In order to perform analyses of data, one must be able to get the data into the analysis system. In some cases data are input directly, but more often in modern times, data are imported or read in from existing storage in one or more files. Ease of access to files of various formats is a required property of any good statistical software package.

2.1.4 Data inspection and manipulation/transformation capabilities

Once data are read in and stored in a system, the ability to explore, view, and manipulate data is crucial to performing exploratory analyses, and the ability to transform data into different structures and create new, derivative variables, or perform “feature engineering,” is also mandatory.

2.1.5 Graphical capabilities

Visual inspection of data is another crucial aspect of exploratory data analysis, and is also necessary to perform various diagnostics following regression and other predictive modeling analyses. The ability to reasonably easily produce a variety of types of plots or graphs and modify them as needed (such as the placement of the legend or the combination of multiple graphs into a single composite) is an important capability.

2.1.6 Breadth and depth of available analyses

Research in statistical and machine learning methodologies has led to an enormous array of different methods available for application in data analyses. While more introductory methods are applied more widely, more complex methods have become much more widely used in recent years, and any general-purpose statistical package needs to offer a substantial array of methods in order to be considered competitive with any of several products that offer literally hundreds of different types of analyses.

2.1.7 Presentation of results, including useful output

As mentioned earlier, graphical capabilities are an important part of a good statistical package. However, useful tabular results and saving of results to files are also mandatory in order for analysts to be able to make appropriate use of a modern statistical package. Publishing in modern journals requires the ability to produce various types of tables in a publication quality layout, and in specific formats such as HTML, LaTeX, or Microsoft Word.

2.1.8 Ease of use, including accessibility

Even the most capable of programs is not particularly helpful if it's very difficult to use. The ease of use of the same program will differ for users of differing levels of ability in terms of statistical

knowledge and programming skills, but any developer of a program they seek to make widely used needs to consider ease of use. Accessibility to those with disabilities is an important part of this for general purpose packages, particularly those seeking to be used in government and school contexts.

2.1.9 Documentation, including algorithmic details

Providing fairly comprehensive and easily followed documentation contributes greatly to ease of use and general utility of statistical software. While many general software programs count on being easy to use with little documentation, those for statistical analyses would be well advised to not attempt this approach, as much about statistics and probability is not intuitive, and explicit details are of particular value in a statistical context. In addition to text description and examples illustrating analyses, providing sufficient algorithmic detail on computations sets good software apart from less serious programs.

Documentation may be seen as somewhat separate from the actual software code, but it is an important aspect of the usability of software. Information on software usage is often provided by official or unofficial online user communities in addition to official written documentation, and the quality of such community information is often a function of the popularity of the software. Thus although not a direct part of the software, the popularity of a program can be an important aspect, both for current usage and for possible future usability, and is something that instructors in particular might consider, as they will want to help their students learn how to work with software that they can make good use of after they finish school.

3. Types of Interfaces

3.1 A classification of interface types

While perhaps not exhaustive or definitive in its breakdown of types of statistical software interfaces, the following list covers the primary approaches to presentation of functional capabilities in statistical software programs, beginning with the most basic, requiring more knowledge and programming skills on the part of the user to programs increasingly designed to be easy to use for those with less knowledge.

1. Command line/script programming
2. Integrated Development Environment (IDE) such as RStudio
3. Graphical point and click overlay of scripting/programming
4. Graphical interface without access to underlying code
5. Automated analytics based on simple selections/inputs
6. Generative AI based

3.1.1 Command line/script programming

The oldest and simplest type of interface to create is one that requires the user to type commands or code into a command line interface or to create a program file with lines of code instructions to be interpreted and executed by the program. All software requires that some form of code instructions be provided in order to execute inputs and produce desired outcomes, but programs differ in how such code is generated.

Command line or script programming interfaces require the most knowledge on the part of the user and returns the most control and flexibility over program functioning of any of the interface options in return for this knowledge and programming skill. Such programs are often very efficient in terms of computational speed and memory requirements, storing data in working memory, at the minor cost of requiring the explicit loading or importing of packages or functions before they can be called. Most statistical programs offer at least some enhancement to this, as while it can be fine for experienced, knowledgeable analysts, the blank space or blinking cursor can be very intimidating to novice users, and at this point, almost every widely-used statistical program at least wraps the coding interface inside some kind of a structure that might be called an IDE or integrated development

environment, allowing the user to more easily switch between writing or executing code and viewing formatted output, graphs, or examining data in an organized structure rather than simply output to a screen or file.

3.1.2 Integrated Development Environment (IDE) such as RStudio

One way to maintain the comprehensiveness and flexibility of a full-fledged coding environment without requiring the user to assume such total control is to wrap command line or programming script coding instructions in an integrated development environment (IDE) or similar structure. With an IDE wrapper on a programming structure the user is still required to create code to execute in order to perform the many functions required for statistical analysis, but they have the ability to do things like easily visualizing raw data, keep track of files and packages or routines, as well as computed objects, and to create integrated files containing program code and output via things like markdown files. Easy access to documentation is another useful aspect of some IDEs, where the user can see some documentation in one window while also having access to the programming area and other context windows.

3.1.3 Graphical point and click overlay of scripting/programming

Graphical interfaces are very popular for software in general, and the same is true for statistical programs. Combining programming or scripting inputs with a graphical user interface (GUI) structure that allows the user to create pieces of code to accomplish various functions can allow novice or less experienced users to begin using a statistical program much more quickly than when a program requires manual construction of all commands. Executing simple, commonly used functions via pointing and clicking can be much faster than writing out and submitting code, and the memory load on the user can be substantially reduced for many purposes by provision of a good GUI. Many users consider this structure, where most functions can be specified via a GUI, with the ability to create scripts via GUI specifications, to be the optimal compromise between ease of use and comprehensive flexibility via programming.

3.1.4 Graphical interface without access to underlying code

Most of the popular features of GUI offerings discussed above are also characteristic of systems offering only the GUI option to submit instructions. This approach can be even less intimidating for novice users without programming experience than a system offering both a GUI and code submission options. However, offering only a GUI generally imposes some restrictions on functionality, and given the sheer number of different functions and types of analyses that might be made available in a comprehensive modern statistical package, this approach is limited by the space available to present options to the user. It is also not as efficient in cases where many repeated specifications are required as an interface that allows creation of code that can be copied and pasted, edited as necessary, and saved for later use. The latter issue may be ameliorated by providing a function to record series of point and click operations that can be recalled and executed again in the future, particularly if it is easy to edit the operations to adjust to similar but not identical needs.

3.1.5 Automated analytics based on simple selections/inputs

In recent decades programs have been released that attempt to put various levels of statistical functionality in the hands of almost anyone. This includes programs that produce descriptive statistics, graphical representations, and in some cases associational analyses (typically involving two variables at a time) given only specification of which variables or features of a data set that are of interest. Some such programs also provide automated modeling features where the user only needs to specify which variable or feature is to be predicted and which others are to be used in modeling. The types of analyses available can include a variety of sophisticated regression and tree-based models. These programs are typically more popular and are usually aimed at users in business contexts, where scientific explanation may be considered less important than prediction.

3.1.6 Generative AI based

Finally, in recent years, with the advent of large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT, many attempts have been made to use natural language interfaces based on LLMs to allow users to request

statistical analyses. In theory, this represents something of a pinnacle in ease of use, requiring even less knowledge and preparation on the part of users than any of the above options. However, there are reasons to exercise a great deal of caution when using LLM-based options for statistical analyses.

Early evaluations of LLMs such as ChatGPT for use in data analysis have produced decidedly mixed results. While ChatGPT has shown some promise as an adjunct to other software and human guidance, relying on it for complete analyses appears to be very risky (see, e.g., Ignjatović & Stevanović, 2023; Jahangiri, 2023; Ordak, 2023; Huang et al., 2024; Ruta et al., 2025). We are still in the early days of LLM-based approaches to data analysis, and technologies are evolving rapidly, so what is true today may not be true in the future. However, there are some structural reasons to exercise caution.

One major concern is that those who are most likely to try to make extensive and/or exclusive use of chat bot interfaces for data analysis are those for whom relying on the results are the most dangerous. Research so far has indicated that the value of what comes out of prompts to LLM-based analysis systems can depend crucially on the amount of detail and specificity of the prompts, and those who may feel the most need for this kind of help are likely to be those least likely to provide the levels of detail and specificity required to obtain accurate, reliable results. Novice users may also have the least understanding of how LLMs work and the fact that their results can be far from trustworthy. Even in simpler cases where LLMs are consulted for help with coding, taking the results for granted can be dangerous. They generally produce what seem to be highly likely outputs given the inputs and their training data, and in many cases these results are useful, but trusting them completely seems likely to remain hazardous in any domain where the results of an analysis are important. They may also produce different results given the exact same data and prompts, making reproducibility difficult.

4. Recommendations

Just as there are almost always multiple reasonable ways to analyze data depending on one's goals and assumptions, which type of user interface is the most useful in a statistical software program can depend on a variety of factors. For seasoned programmers experienced in statistical analyses, command line or scripting interfaces may be preferred, as they allow the most direct access to the back end of a program where computations are performed. They also can be much lighter and faster in terms of computer memory requirements than programs with extensive GUI components. They will seldom be the options of choice for novice users and those with little statistical knowledge, and those who seek to teach introductory or intermediate-level courses may want to consider whether they have the time and resources to provide the level of help required for many students to make productive use of such programs. As with any option, easy access to a history or log of executed commands should be a prerequisite to facilitate reproducibility.

The wrapping of command line or scripting interfaces in IDEs can go a fair way towards bending the learning curve for such programs. IDEs such as RStudio and Jupyter and other notebooks for Python have become very popular, though they still require coding beyond the level desired by many students and applied practitioners without substantial coding experience. For those who plan to work in analytics, learning to code in a widely used environment such as R, which offers extremely broad and deep statistical analysis capabilities, as well as the ability to write custom routines, is probably well worth the investment of time and effort. For those willing to learn how to code, pretty much any extant statistical analyses may be performed via R/RStudio, which offers probably the most complete set of analysis options.

Major commercial statistical packages such as SAS Viya, IBM SPSS Statistics, and Stata all offer means to connect to and run R scripts and Python programs, so for those who want access to the full statistical functionality of R, working entirely within R is not required. Of course, these programs have financial costs that may make them less attractive than free programs like R or Python. These costs do sometimes include access to support and user communities that may make them

worthwhile, though the continued growth of communities for R and Python might continue to reduce the relative value of communities for commercial software products.

Programs offering GUI overlays to code or command syntax such as IBM SPSS Statistics or Stata retain popularity among many students and others who prefer to spend less time coding. At this point, the development of so many different types of statistical analyses has made it complicated to design a graphical interface with menus that can display all the available analysis options without potentially confusing or overwhelming the user. For example, the Analyze option in IBM SPSS Statistics has in some areas three levels of drop-down menus to navigate to select certain analyses. Stata, which has more statistical functionality, has in some areas four levels of drop-down menus under its Statistics option. As analytic options continue to be developed, the utility of graphical presentations may diminish substantially, as choosing analyses from hundreds of options can be less convenient than choosing from a more limited set of options.

For coursework and applications that are constrained to more introductory or perhaps intermediate types of analyses, GUI interfaces that only offer limited options may retain some utility. Graphical interfaces that do not offer access to the underlying commands or code created may be attractive to those who do not wish to deal with code at all, but if these programs do not provide good ways to document and reproduce data transformations and statistical analyses, their utility for serious work is likely to be severely limited.

Many analysts working in commercial spaces find utility in programs that largely automate data analysis and feature engineering. Such programs may not provide easy access to document and reproduce variable or feature transformations or statistical or machine learning analyses, and where this is the case, their use is to be discouraged in scientific contexts. Similarly, lack of sufficient documentation of how they work can make their use hazardous when applied to important analyses. Handing over this level of control to a program can be inviting, but has its dangers, as assumptions and methods that are inappropriate for a given problem may be applied without the user knowing this is happening.

Finally, ChatGPT and other LLM-based chat bot interface programs are currently of limited utility for most users in serious statistical analysis contexts. They may be very useful as adjuncts to other programs and user-controlled analyses, particularly in providing easy access to code or command syntax snippets, but even in these limited contexts the user needs to confirm that the code or command syntax is correct and produces the desired results. So-called LLM hallucinations have included suggesting the use of nonexistent commands for statistical analyses.

At this time it seems that in order to obtain correct and appropriate analytic results from chat bots, the user needs to have a level of knowledge and the patience to provide prompts at a level of detail and specificity that not very many analysts will have, at least not those who are unwilling to use dedicated statistical or machine learning software programs. In all cases, the nature of LLM functioning requires the user to have the ability to independently confirm the results when accuracy matters. The rapid development of artificial intelligence programs might eventually render this assessment obsolete, perhaps even fairly soon, but for now the use of chat bots for statistical analyses requires a great deal of caution.

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